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June 2022

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ONWUBIKO, EMMANUEL CHIDIADI, "An Empirical study of the Influence of Knowledge Sharing Behaviors and Organizational Culture on Staff Performance in University Libraries" (2022). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7166.

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An Empirical study of the Influence of Knowledge Sharing Behaviors and Organizational Culture on Staff Performance in University Libraries

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Abstract

Knowledge sharing has been shown to improve individual and organization performance and innovativeness as a result, has become increasingly important to organizations as most organizations are now considered to operate in a knowledge economy. This study therefore investigated knowledge sharing practice as well as organizational culture and their effect on performance of staff of university libraries. The study employed a survey design with a population sample of 79 library staff derived through purposive sampling techniques from two university libraries in Nigeria. The principle instrument used for data collection was a four-point Likert scale structured questionnaire validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation while the study was guided by four research questions and one formulated and tested null hypothesis. The data collected were analyzed using frequency and simple percentages whereas the only null hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regressions. The result of this study did reveal that most library staff keep to punctuality/regularity in work and timely accomplishment of their given task as well as show great commitment to general library duties and exhibit ability to meet the library set objectives and deadline. The study also discovered that organizational culture prevalent in university library were in the area of customers' (Users) satisfaction, structure, commitment and communication. The outcome of this study also revealed the various knowledge sharing practices of the library staff to include: departmental/unit meetings, general meetings, face-to-face interactions, periodical unit-by-unit meetings, informal interaction sessions, report writing, training and whatsapp group. The study as well found that there were seven major factors militating against knowledge sharing in the university library which invariably affect staff performance. These include; lack of trust among staff; staff idiosyncrasy; lack of organizational policy on knowledge sharing, inhibiting factors of staff performance, inadequate managerial skills, poor verbal/written

communication and interpersonal skills and discriminatory attitude of university librarian towards staff. The result of the study further revealed that occupational culture and knowledge sharing practices have significant influence in staff performance in university libraries. It is based on the findings and identified challenges facing effective knowledge sharing practices by staff in the university library that recommendations were made which include among other ones that the behavior of the library management needs to symbolize the kinds of values and behaviors that should be realized in every unit/department of the university library on the ground that as change agents, they are keys to the success of this cultural change process and important communicators of new values, university librarians must appreciate their role in maintaining or evolving an organization's culture and that management of university libraries should note that for them to get the best out of every staff of the library in terms of performance and knowledge sharing, each staff should be seen as more valuable than the organization itself.

Keywords: Organizational culture, Knowledge Sharing, Staff Performance, University Library, Knowledge management,

1.0. Introduction

Knowledge a product of information, understanding or skills acquired through education is principal determinant of how a staff excel in any given task or responsibility. Invariably, the performance of any staff in any work place depends on the knowledge of the given staff in line with the culture of the organisation, institution or firm. Suffice to say, that staff performance is a basic parameter for measuring any institution or organization's success and the realization of its goals and mission. This implies that staff performance is basically how well a job related activities expected of a worker were executed (Wang, 2004). Performance therefore is constituted by actions that are scalable and measurable, in that different elements like training, welfare skills, communication, motivations management policies, fringe benefits, promotion dedication, salary and other welfare packages are on the threshold of encourage staff to be at their best and discharge their assigned responsibilities with utmost sincerity. The university libraries no doubt like any other institution have come to realize that staff are catalyst that

transforms a system into tangible products and without doubt makes it possible for performance to determine the achievement the realization of the organization's goals and vision in their entirety (Mueller, Wallace & Price, 1996)

It is against this backdrop that that the improvement of the performance of employees in many production and service organisations and institutions has been in the front burner of stakeholders and researchers. This on the premise that performance is yet to reach the expected level as a result of the adverse effect of poor knowledge sharing practices among employees in these institutions and organizations. The implication is that by supporting knowledge creation through sharing, such institution so to speak can influence staff performance, minimize staff turnover intentions as well as increase their business returns and academic libraries being service oriented institution need highly performing staff if they are to realize their mission of supporting the tripartite functions of the university which are; teaching/learning, research and extension services through the delivering of sustainable services to their esteemed customers and this can only be realized if the libraries embrace efficient and effective organizational culture that guarantees knowledge sharing practices among staff which will enhance the overall performance of the staff.

Organizational culture as define by Martins and Coetzee (2007) are values, assumptions and norms believed to improve employee's functional capacity and facilitate the attainment of the organizational goals and objectives Organizational culture also includes an organization's expectations, experiences, philosophy, as well as the values that guide member behavior and is expressed in member self-image, inner workings, interactions with the outside world, and future expectations while culture is based on shared attitudes, beliefs, customs, and written and unwritten rules that have been developed over time and are considered valid (The Business Dictionary).as well as the organization's vision, values, norms, systems, symbols, language, assumptions, beliefs, and habits (Needle, 2004).

The belief is that organizational culture influences and guides the action of an individual negatively or positively in any given set-up and this has in recent time received much consideration as a result of its perceived influence in staff performance. As explained by Abdullahi (2004), the influence of organizational influence towards employee performance is often seen from staff's result orientation and how decision is made, who did what, how reward is

applied, who is promoted, how staff is treated, how the organization responds to its environment among others. The broad term is that Knowledge sharing within an organization has often been asserted as a necessary practice for success and sustainability of its staff performance imbedded under organizational culture. In other words, high level manpower is needed in the case of the university library to deliver sustainable services to her esteemed users and this can only be achieved with the adoption of efficient organizational culture that supports effective knowledge sharing practices among the library staff and in this regard, such an issue cannot be treated with kid-glove when we know that university libraries more so in Nigeria have performance challenges.

1.2. Statement of the Problems

Staff performance in any organization can make or mar the growth of such organization as high level performance will definitely contribute to the growth and success of the organization. Closely associated with staff performance is high knowledge sharing among staff in line with the organizational culture which the staff member envisaged to be favorable to their well-being. In recent years experience has shown that staffs working in university libraries in Nigeria (which may not be peculiar) are not willing to share knowledge acquired either as a result of in-the-job experience, seminars, conferences and their like with their colleagues and this has resulted to unhealthy rivalry among staff. This act could be intentional or unintentional targeted at positioning such a staff as the most outstanding so as to be favored by the boss. This scenario no doubt is a wind that blows no good as it negatively affects the overall productivity and achievement of the library directly or indirectly. Furthermore it makes the harnessing of individual staff performance as to boosting the overall service delivery of the library a big challenging issue on resolved. In treating the variables, literature shows that only very few studies have without cleared definition discussed of organizations' cultural factors influencing knowledge management and sharing. It is against this back drop that this study was embarked upon as to closing the identified gap in knowledge through an empirical study of the effect of knowledge sharing practices and organizational culture on the performance of staff using university libraries as a case in point.

1.3. Research Objectives

This study apart from the principle objective which is to establish the effect of knowledge sharing and organizational culture on staff performance was geared towards achieving the following objectives:

- 1) To ascertain the level of staff performance in university libraries
- 2) Determine knowledge sharing practices that are common in the libraries
- 3) Determine the effect of knowledge sharing practices and organizational culture on staff performance
- 4) Determine factors militating against effective knowledge sharing practices in university libraries.

1.4. Research Questions

- 1) What is the level of staff performance in university libraries?
- 2) What knowledge practices are common in university libraries?
- 3) What effect(s) do knowledge sharing practices and organizational culture have on staff performance in university libraries?
- 4) What are the factors militating against effective knowledge sharing practices in university libraries?

1.5 Hypothesis

H01: Organizational culture and knowledge sharing practices have no statistically significant influence on staff performance in the university libraries

2.0. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Framework

2.1.1, Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge, information, data, regardless of the nomenclature, it all powers your business. Knowledge is the key to fundamental element that determines the level of development of any organization or nation. These intangibles lie at the heart of your commercial success and are

what separate you from your competitors. Put simply, knowledge sharing is the capture, management and distribution of key information within your business. It typically involves the identification of the essential data that drives your success, data that is more often than not, locked in the heads of your employees. This can be anything from optimization tips, to business-critical information around your company strengths and weakness or just information on processes and how they work. Whatever the case, all these data flows play a critical role in the everyday operation of your business, and so they need to be accessible to the right people in the right place, at the right time. This is what knowledge sharing achieves. It's the systems, processes and philosophy around information in your organization (Document360 Team, 2022)

Knowledge sharing may be defined in various ways depending on the context in which it is considered. Van Den Hooff and De Ridder (2004) conceptualization of knowledge sharing portrays it as a "process where individuals mutually exchange their implicit (tacit) and explicit knowledge to create new knowledge" According to De Vrie, Van Den Hooff and De Ridder (2006), this definition implies that knowledge sharing behavior consists of

- ❖ the supply of new knowledge and
- ❖ the demand for new knowledge (Wabwezi, 2011)

As explained by Bukowitz, & Williams, (1999) and Serban, & Luan, (2002), Knowledge sharing is an activity through which knowledge (namely, information, skills, or expertise) is exchanged among people, friends, peers, families, communities (for example, Wikipedia), or within or between organizations. It bridges the individual and organizational knowledge, improving the absorptive and innovation capacity and thus leading to sustained competitive advantage of companies as well as individuals (Ipe, 2003). According to Dalkir (2005), knowledge sharing is part of the Knowledge management process. Knowledge management on its own is defined as the process of creating, storing, applying and re-using organizational knowledge to enable an organization achieve its goals and objectives in terms of resources, documents and people's skills (IFLA, 2009). IFLA further states that knowledge management is extending the concept of knowledge beyond existing concepts like 'memory' 'storage' and 'information' to include such items as tacit knowledge, implicit knowledge, explicit knowledge and procedural knowledge adding that it offers the approach for creating knowledge to leverage the intellectual capital and

knowledge assets of an organization. According to Hussain, Lucas and Ali (2004), knowledge management is fundamentally the management of corporate knowledge and intellectual assets that can improve a range of organizational performance characteristics and add value by enabling an enterprise act more intelligently. They added that it helps organizations identify, select, organize, disseminate and transfer important information and experience that are a part of the organizational memory that typically resides within the organization in an unstructured manner helping in effective and efficient problem solving, dynamic learning, strategic planning and decision making. While Newman (n.d) cited in Ajiferuke (2013), sees it as a collection of processes that govern the creation, dissemination and utilization of knowledge in an organization.

2.1.2. Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is defined as the underlying beliefs, assumptions, values and ways of interacting that contribute to the unique social and psychological environment of an organization. Organizational culture includes an organization's expectations, experiences, philosophy, as well as the values that guide member behavior, and is expressed in member self-image, inner workings, interactions with the outside world, and future expectations (Cancialosi, 2017). Culture is based on shared attitudes, beliefs, customs, and written and unwritten rules that have been developed over time and are considered valid. Culture also includes the organization's vision, values, norms, systems, symbols, language, assumptions, beliefs, and habits (Needle, 2004). Simply stated, organizational culture is "the way things are done around here" (Deal & Kennedy, 2000).

While the above definitions of culture express how the construct plays out in the workplace, other definitions stress employee behavioral components, and how organizational culture directly influences the behaviors of employees within an organization. Under this set of definitions, organizational culture is a set of shared assumptions that guide what happens in organizations by defining appropriate behavior for various situations (Ravasi & Schultz, 2006). Organizational culture affects the way people and groups interact with each other, with clients, and with stakeholders. Also, organizational culture may influence how much employees identify with their organization (Schrodt, 2002).

2.1.3. Staff Performance

The efficient and effective use of one's abilities is called performance. In terms of a library staff's performance both the intellectual and physical aspects of providing services are taken into consideration by researchers (Tahir, Saba, & Rabbia, 2013). The ability of employees to utilize their competencies to achieve the goals of the organization is called work performance (Campbell, 1990). In the case of teachers, work performance is studied in terms of teachers' ability to reshape their behaviour in accordance with the changing work environment and successfully complete the given assignment (Marsh, 1987; Medley, 1982). In a professional environment a person has to work in groups that consist of individuals who have different opinions and ideas. Knowledge sharing can help bridge any differences that might be magnified due to poor knowledge on the part of the staffs, thus creating stronger teams (Ashforth & Humphrey, 1995). (Jamshidi, Bagherzadeh, & Nikoo) stated that performance refers to an individual's ability to achieve the targets set for him/her. This involves the volume of output in terms of sales or production and it can be compared with the organizational standard. The performance of person is based on pre-determined targets. The successful achievement of these targets are often based on mental processes that are not visible, including rational thought, decision-making and puzzle solving skills (Bailey & Robert, 2003). Performance evaluation of employees is based on how the given tasks are performed and whether or not they aid in the achievement of the organizational goals (Soltani & Iraj 2003) as cited in (Ali, 2013). (Winarno, 2008) states that the proof of performance can be found in the products and services produced by an individual or group. (Shahzad, Sarmad, Abbas, & Khan, 2010) on the other hand state, that performance is the result of any activity over a specific time period.

2.2. Empirical and Theoretical Framework

As noted by Tharp (2012), researches have been carried out on various issues on organizational culture which include organizational culture types that emphasized the stages of culture across the organization and organizational psychology which focuses on how culture makes an impact on employee psychology and performance (Schein, 1999 & Dension, 2000). In their study, Adkins and Caldwell (2004) discovered that job satisfaction was positively associated with the

degree to which employees fit into both the overall culture and subculture in which they worked in that a perceived mismatch of the organization's culture and what employees felt the culture should be is related to a number of negative consequences including lower job satisfaction, higher job strain, general stress and turnover intent. According to Devis (2007), organizational culture has been linked to economic performance and organization viability as organization with good culture that is dedicated to continuous improvement and focus on core values, is more financially successful and gives positive effect on employees in long-term. (Nazir & Zamir, 2015).

As noted by Schein (1999) and Dension (2000) in their separate studies, organizations which include university libraries can achieve their maximum level of effectiveness and efficiency through an established link between organizational culture and employees' performance. Other studies that indicated that there exist relationship between organisational culture and staff performance include; Sun (2008) and Motilewa, Agboola & Adeniji (2015). It is in line with the above that Magee (2002) did aver that organizational culture is inherently connected to organizational practices, therefore added Schmidt, Shull and Scmitt (2005), organizational performance is conditional on organizational culture and employees' performance could translate into organizational outcomes such as users' satisfaction as in the case of the library. Prior to the above findings, Renn and Vandenberg (1995) did in a research conducted, demonstrated a conceptual linkage between organizational culture and employee performance, while some organizations believe that culture is theoretically related to performance and do have positive influence on it, thus cultural system of an organization determines the coordination of tasks and minimizes inefficiency in managing employees' effort and firms resources (Martin & Siehl, 1990) and others see performance as a dependent variable which seeks to recognize other independent variables that produce variations in its performance.

Literature also shows that there are researchers who considered the importance of individual factors such as ability and effort to create an interface between organizational culture and staff performance (Gardener & Schermerhorn, 2004; Schermerhorn et al., 1990). To Furnham and Gunter (1993), organizational culture functions as internal integration and coordination between organization's operations and its employees describing internal integration as the societal interaction of new members with the existing ones thereby creating boundaries of the organization feelings of identity among potentials and commitment to the organization. As

revealed by Furnhorn and Gunter (1993), shared system which forms the basis of communication and mutual understanding in an organization is due to the culture and if the organizational culture fails to fulfill these functions at satisfactory level, the culture may have significant negative influence on the efficiency of the employees.

Furthermore, theorist have also argued that sustainable competitive advantage arises from the formulation of organizational competencies which are both superior and incorrectly imitable by competitors (Saar Pe're & Garcia-Falcon, 2002). On the other hand revealed Denison, Daniel, Harland and Goelzer (2004), practitioners and academicians suggested that the performance of an organization is dependent on the degree in which the values of the culture are comprehensively shared but what structure that is in place to allow such sharing to thrive explicitly is worthy of note.

On how knowledge sharing can be achieve within an organization, available reviewed literature indicated that knowledge sharing is divided into three strains with several theories utilized to explain why and how knowledge sharing should be achieved within organizations (Chin & Kwot, 2008; Hse, 2008; wang, 2004; Lin & Lee, 2006). The three strains as highlighted include; 'resources based theory', 'transaction cost theory' and 'social capital theory' while methodology such as 'multiple methods and tools' are used to facilitate knowledge sharing as they concern system planning, system reengineering, and communication system and sharing as in sharing within and between organizations. While Taminiou, Smit, and De Lange (2007) present two forms of knowledge sharing as formal knowledge sharing and informal knowledge sharing (as cited in Wabwezi, 2011).

The goal of knowledge sharing in the three strands as asserted by Hse (2008) is to improve organizations competitiveness inasmuch as the first two strands as very paramount in facilitating knowledge sharing, the final decision on whether to share or not solely rest on the employee with the anticipated reward to be received or required as the main determinant. Lee and Ahn (2006) on their part developed a model that links knowledge sharing to two types of reward system; individual-based reward system based on individual contribution of valuable knowledge and group-based reward system which is based on collective contribution of the entire group in knowledge sharing that improves organizational performance. The outcome shows that

individual-based reward system is more efficient than group-based system. It was noted that in the group-based system, knowledgeable staffs are less likely to share their knowledge. However, Siemsen, Roth and Balashubramanian (2008) utilized a well-established motivational framework that includes opportunity and ability to explain employees' knowledge sharing behaviors. Their result suggested that a constraining-factor model acts as a new perspective and can explain employees' knowledge sharing behaviors by demonstrating that motivation does not always improve knowledge sharing but is contingent upon other conditions. In a related development, Kuo and Young (2008) propounded a research model based on 'theory of Reasoned Actions' (TRA) and 'Theory of Planned Behavior' (TPB) that predicts that knowledge sharing intention behavior is a function of attitude, objective, norms and perceived behavior control. They argued that self-efficacy directly predicts knowledge sharing behavior. Yang and Konrad (2010) corroborated the above notion as they posit that individual attitude towards knowledge sharing and storing has significant influence on organizational knowledge sharing. This assertion affirms the fact that individuals' attitudes towards learning and sharing knowledge impact organizational knowledge impact.

Haas and Hansen (2007) claim that knowledge sharing has been shown to improve individual and organization performance and innovativeness. They added that knowledge sharing is a practice that has become increasingly important to organizations as most organizations are now considered to operate in a knowledge economy. Knowledge sharing in an organization not only occurs at the individual level but also at the collective level (Obembe, 2010). Obembe further states that an organization's capacity for knowledge sharing is crucial as a factor in the ability to generate new knowledge as well as its ability to utilize the resources and capabilities of its members. Knowledge sharing affects not only tacit knowledge but all phases of the knowledge creating process (Wabwezi, 2011). Document360 Team (2022), reveals that Businesses with good knowledge sharing capabilities are able to ensure their workforce have access to the information they need to do the best job possible. In addition, effective knowledge sharing also ensures companies are able to protect themselves from unexpected employee turnover. This is particularly crucial, because it helps to avoid information losses that can potentially cripple your business

In another development, Hsu (2008) in a study of knowledge sharing in a manufacturing company in Taiwan discovered the three organizational practices that can enhance employees' tendencies to share their knowledge as: continuous company wide-learning initiatives, performance management systems and information disclosure to create a sharing climate. As declared by Du, Ai and Ren (2007), knowledge sharing has its relationship in a long run performance and competitiveness. There have also been studies on benefits, necessities and contents of knowledge sharing with none tailored towards discussing the relationship between knowledge sharing and performance and this has been a great challenge towards building a quantitative theory of knowledge sharing towards performance by researchers (Du et al., 2007).

On the means of sharing knowledge, apart from traditional face-to-face knowledge sharing writes Yao et al (2021), social media is a good tool because it is convenient, efficient, and widely used adding that in the digital world, websites and mobile applications enable knowledge or talent sharing between individuals and/or within teams. The individuals can easily reach the people who want to learn and share their talent to get rewarded.

3.0. Methodology

The study employed a survey design research method with a population sample of 79 library staff derived through purposive sampling techniques from two federal university libraries in Nigeria; Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka Library (40) and Bayero University, Kano library (39). The study was guided by four research questions and one formulated and tested null hypothesis while the principle instrument used for data collection was a four-point Likert scale structured questionnaire validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation as well as observations. The instrument was pre-tested for reliability among staff of Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana in Ebonyi State, Nigeria and the overall Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient value stood at 0.90. The data collected were analyzed using frequency and simple percentages in line with the objectives of the study whereas the only null hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regressions.

4.0. Presentation and Analysis of Data

The data collected for this study are presented in tables and a figure in line with research objectives and the formulated null hypothesis.

Table 1: Staff performance in academic libraries

Appraisal of staff performance	Excellent		Very good		Good		Fair	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Punctuality/regularity at work	40	50.63	25	31.65	10	12.65	4	5.1
Ability to meet the library set objectives and deadline	20	25.31	23	29.11	11	13.92	25	31.64
Ability to work as a team player creatively and diligently	21	26.58	13	16.45	15	19	30	37.97
Timely response to users request	4	5.06	45	56.96	20	25.31	10	12.65
Ability to work with minimum supervision	15	18.98	10	12.65	30	37.97	24	30.37
Timely task accomplishment	35	44.30	24	30.37	19	24.05	11	13.92
Effort put in is commensurate with result obtained	23	29.11	12	15.18	10	12.65	34	43.03
Prompt submission of report of assigned responsibility	12	15.18	8	10.12	30	37.97	29	36.70
Commitment to general library duties	34	43.03	15	18.98	13	16.45	17	21.51
Skill enhancement through on the job training	23	29.11	8	10.12	12	15.18	26	32.91

The data as shown in table 1 as obtained in section ‘A’ of the questionnaire were exclusively provided by ‘Heads of Unit whose duty it was to annually appraise their staff performances. The data revealed that the staff exhibit high level of punctuality/regularity in work as 65 or 82.28% out of 79 respondents fall under excellent or very good while under timely accomplishment of task, 69 respondents representing 87.34 % were within excellent or very good. On commitment to general library duties 49 or % of the respondents fall within excellent or very good and Ability to meet the library set objectives and deadline-43 respondents or 54.43% performed excellently well or very good. On the other hand prompt submission of report of assigned responsibility, skill enhancement through on the job training were rated below average under the scale of excellent and very good as only 20 or 25.31% and 31 representing 39.24% respectively were within these levels. Others were ‘ability to work as a team player creatively and diligently-43.03% or 34 respondents performed excellently or very good and effort put in is commensurate with result-44.30-% or 35 respondents were graded excellent or very good.

Table 2: Organizational culture of university libraries

Organizational culture	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%

Communication of new idea to staff is supported by the library	45	56.86	19	24.05	9	11.39	6	7.59
The library supports the realization of the tripartite functions of the university (teaching/learning, research & extension services)	50	63.29	29	36.70	-	-	-	-
The library provides resources to satisfy information needs of both faculty and students	45	56.96	34	43.03	-	-	-	-
Information is often passed across from university-librarian to unit heads in the library	50	63.29	29	36.70	-	-	-	-
The library is involved in library cooperation	10	31.64	12	15.18	30	37.97	27	34.17
The library does not place emphasis in team- work	49	62.92	20	25.31	4	5.06	6	7.59
The library has formal communication channel	29	36.70	25	31.64	11	13.92	14	17.72
The most utilized channel of communication in the library is electronics (email, sms, whatsapp etc)	12	15.18	35	44.30	19	24.05	15	18.98
The library has zero tolerance for trust	37	46.83	21	26.58	16	20.25	5	6.32
Decisions are often made based on reports submitted by management without verification of the effect on staff	50	63.29	16	20.23	8	10.12	5	6.32
The library has formal structure of administration	5	6.33	59	74.68	10	12.65	5	6.32
Most library staff are not trust worthy	54	68.35	12	15.18	7	8.86	6	7.59

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree

The data as displayed in table 2 above showed that the numero-uno of the organizational culture of the university library was/is 'the library supports for the realization of the tripartite functions of the university (teaching/learning, research & extension services) as 79 or 100% of the respondents indicated strongly agree or agree to the item, this was followed by the library provides resources to satisfy information needs of both faculty and students with 45 respondents or 56.97% indicating ;strongly agree; and 34 or 43.03% indicating 'agree' which shows 100% response of 'agree. Another item that score 100% response of 'strongly agree or agree was Information is often passed across from university-librarian to unit heads in the library. On the contrary, the respondents 100% agreed that the university library does not encourage teamwork while 66 of them or 83.54% strongly agreed or agreed that most library staffs are not trust worthy

Table 3: Knowledge sharing practices of university libraries staff

Knowledge sharing practices	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Departmental/unit information is shared during meetings	37	46.83	42	53.16	-	-	-	-
Staffs are encouraged to share information during departmental meetings	14	17.72	8	10.12	29	36.70	28	35.44

Face-to-face information is preferred by staff as it is the most encouraged by library management	20	25.31	42	53.16	10	12.65	7	8.86
Use of Whatsapp group and other social media	59	74.68	20	25.31	-	-	-	.
Regular trainings ensure effective knowledge sharing among staff	5	6.32	15	18.98	30	37.97	29	36.70
The library recommends report writing after each training as to share experiential knowledge	7	8.86	13	16.45	24	30.37	35	44.30
The library shares knowledge of improved service to staff during general meetings	34	43.03	29	36.70	13	16.45	3	3.79
Periodical unit-by-unit meetings are often held to enlighten staff on how to improve existing services	43	54.45	19	24.05	10	12.65	7	8.86
I learn from mistakes shared by colleagues during informal interaction sessions.	12	15.18	35	44.30	23	29.11	9	11.39

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree

The data in table 3 are that of knowledge sharing practices of university libraries staff. As shown, the principle means of sharing knowledge among staff in the library was the Whatsapp and other social media with 100% affirmative followed by departmental/unit meetings which has an SA score of % representing 37 respondents and A score of % or 42 respondents an indication of 100% affirmation, another means of sharing knowledge among the staff is through general meeting with 34 respondents (48.83%) strongly agreed and 29 or 36.70% agreed which shows that of the 79 respondents, 63 answered in the positive. Other knowledge sharing practices were: face-to-face interactions- 62 respondents or 78.48%, periodical unit-by-unit meetings-78.48% or 62 respondents, informal interaction sessions-47 respondents or 59.50%, report writing-25.31% standing for 20 respondents and training with 25.31% score or 20 respondents

Table 4: factors militating against effective knowledge sharing among the library staff

Factors militating against knowledge sharing	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Staff idiosyncrasy	60	75.94	13	16.45	4	5.06	2	2.53
Poor verbal/written communication and interpersonal skills	32	40.50	16	20.25	11	13.92	20	25.31
Inhibiting factors of staff performance	41	51.90	12	15.18	15	18.98	11	13.92
Inadequate managerial skills	20	25.31	30	37.97	13	16.45	16	20.25
Lack of organizational policy on knowledge sharing	55	69.62	5	6.32	12	15.18	7	8.86
Discriminatory attitude of university librarian towards staff	21	26.58	24	30.37	14	17.72	30	37.97
Effect of emerging technology	20	25.31	12	15.18	34	43.03	13	16.45

Lack of trust among staff	40	50.63	35	44.30	3	3.8	1	1.26
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Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree

Figure 1: Graphical representation of factors militating against knowledge sharing among the library staff

Figure 2: Militating factors in bar chart for clarity

The data as displayed in table 1 and figures 1 and 2 showed that of the 8 items stated as factors militating against knowledge sharing practices of staffs in university libraries, 7 were scored above 50% in affirmation while only the emergence of technology scored below 50%. A breakdown shows that lack of trust among staff ranked highest with 95% or 75 respondents affirmative, followed by staff idiosyncrasy with 92.4% representing 93 respondents, on the 3rd position as a challenge was lack of organizational policy on knowledge sharing-75.95% followed by inhibiting factors of staff performance-67.1%. Others were, inadequate managerial skills-63.3%, Poor verbal/written communication and interpersonal skills-60.8% and discriminatory attitude of university librarian towards staff with 57%.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 5: Result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on OC and SP

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	N	R	P	Remark
Organizational Culture	58.8304	6.64036				

Staff Performance	15.3971	3.50289	79	.889***	.001	Sig
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The outcome of the null hypothesis tested using Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) coefficient shows that there is statistical significant ($P < 0.05$) relationship between organizational culture and staff performance in university libraries at a value of $r = .889^{***}$ $N = 79$, $p < 0.05$ and with the calculated p-value .001 less than the p-value 0.05 (significant level) the null hypothesis was then rejected on the ground of the standing law.

Table 6: Result of Pearson Product Moment Coefficient on KSP and SP

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	N	R	P	Remark
Knowledge sharing practices	25.43451	7.48489	79	.693***	.002	Sig
Staff performance	51.70216	4.55001				

Table 6 is a summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient analysis of the relationship between knowledge sharing practices of staff in university library and their performance. The result shows under the value of $r = .693^{***}$ that there is a positive correlation between knowledge sharing and staff performance and since the P-value 0.002 is less than the 0.05 (significant level), the null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Table 7: Result of Multiple Regression on OC, KSP and Staff Performance

Model	Un-standardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	R^2	F	Sig	94.0% Coefficient Internal for Beta	
	B	Std Error	Beta					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1(Constant)	87.82	6.385		14.721	.693	32.381	.000	75.111	100.401
Organizational Culture	-.166	.067	-.277	-2.631			.000	-.587	-.800
Knowledge Sharing Practices	-.384	.053	-.670				.000	-.499	-.709

The result of Multiple Regression analysis of the relationship between organizational culture, knowledge sharing practices and staff performance as summarized in table 7 above shows that under the value $R^2 = .893$ organizational culture and knowledge sharing practices do contribute significantly to staff performance ($F_{3,94} = 32.381$, $p < 0.05$, $R^2 = .693$).

5.0. Discussion of Results

The result of this study did reveal that most library staff keep to punctuality/regularity in work and timely accomplishment of their given task as well as show great commitment to general library duties and exhibit ability to meet the library set objectives and deadline. This shows that most university library staff have good share of their personal performance interwoven into their job outputs. This outcome is in conformity with that of March and Sutton (1997) who observed that most organizations asserts their performance as a dependent variables which seeks to recognize other independent variables that produce variations in its performance and the assertion of Jamshidi, Bagherzadeh, and Nikoo that performance refers to an individual's ability to achieve the targets set for him/her. On the other hand, prompt submission of report of assigned responsibility, skill enhancement through on the job training were rated below average. It was also discovered, that the staff lack the ability to work as a team player creatively and diligently and efforts put in their job most times are not commensurate with their output as it was observed that most of them do not show enough commitment to their given task unless under strict supervision (see table 1).

The study also discovered that organizational culture prevalent in university library were in the area of customers' (Users) satisfaction, structure, commitment and communication. In the area of users' satisfaction, university libraries, the analyzed data revealed that the university library supports the realization of the tripartite functions of the university (teaching/learning, research & extension services) as well as provides resources to satisfy information needs of both faculty and students. The result further reveals that under communication, information is often passed across from university-librarian to unit heads in the library though the university librarian by practice does not encourage teamwork and as noted most library staffs were not trust worthy. All the same, the library may be said to maintain a balanced mode of communication which is formal in structure while face-to-face, use of SMS and whatsapp remained the most prevalent channels of communication. Inasmuch as the library has zero tolerance for staff trust, in practice, it was observed to be out of existence as they discriminate in the line of status, ethnicity, religion and tribe among others while the university library maintains a formal structure of administration. As noted by Schein (2010) leaders are vital to the creation and communication of their workplace culture. In the line of the above, some of the findings in the area of occupational culture were in contrast to the fact that leaders must appreciate their role in maintaining or evolving an

organization's culture. A deeply embedded and established culture illustrates how people should behave, which can help employees achieve their goals. This behavioral framework, in turn, ensures higher job satisfaction when an employee feels a leader is helping him or her complete a goal (Tsai, 2011). From this perspective, organizational culture, leadership, and job satisfaction are all inextricably linked.

The outcome of this study also revealed the various knowledge sharing practices of the library staff to include: departmental/unit meetings, general meetings, face-to-face interactions, periodical unit-by-unit meetings, informal interaction sessions, report writing, training and whatsapp group. The outcome of this study is not far from Yao et al (2021) declaration that apart from traditional face-to-face knowledge sharing and other formal means of communication, social media is a good tool because it is convenient, efficient, and widely used as well as that of Yang and Konrad (2011) who discovered that employee attitude towards learning, sharing and storing have significant influence on organizational knowledge sharing.

The study as well found that there were seven major factors militating against knowledge sharing in the university library which invariably affect staff performance. These include; lack of trust among staff; staff idiosyncrasy; lack of organizational policy on knowledge sharing, inhibiting factors of staff performance, inadequate managerial skills, poor verbal/written communication and interpersonal skills and discriminatory attitude of university librarian towards staff. The above finding no doubt negates Haas and Hansen (2007) claim that knowledge sharing has been shown to improve individual and organization performance and innovativeness. They added that knowledge sharing is a practice that has become increasingly important to organizations as most organizations are now considered to operate in a knowledge economy. Knowledge sharing in an organization not only occurs at the individual level but also at the collective level (Obembe, 2010). Obembe further states that an organization's capacity for knowledge sharing is crucial as a factor in the ability to generate new knowledge as well as its ability to utilize the resources and capabilities of its members. Knowledge sharing affects not only tacit knowledge but all phases of the knowledge creating process (as cited in Wabwezi, 2011).

Furtherance, based on the formulated and tested hypothesis, it was discovered in the first instance, that there is statistical significant ($P < 0.05$) relationship between organizational culture

and staff performance in university libraries (see table 5) and a positive relationship between knowledge sharing practices of staff in university library and their performance (see table 7) while the result of Multiple Regression analysis of the relationship between organizational culture, knowledge sharing practices and staff performance did show that organizational culture and knowledge sharing practices do contribute significantly to staff performance. This result affirms that of by Schein (1999) and Dension (2000) in their separate studies, noted that organizations which include university libraries can achieve their maximum level of effectiveness and efficiency through an established link between organizational culture and employees' performance. Other studies that indicated that there exist relationship between organisational culture and staff performance include; Sun (2008) and Motilewa, Agboola & Adeniji (2015) and also Schmidt, Shull and Scmitt (2005) who added that organizational performance is conditional on organizational culture and employees' performance could translate into organizational outcomes such as users' satisfaction as in the case of the library

5.1. Conclusion and Recommendations

The drawn conclusion based on the outcome of this study, is that organizational culture plays prominent role in the enhancement of staff performance as well as knowledge sharing practices. In other words, occupational culture and knowledge sharing practices have significant influence is staff performance in university libraries. Imperatively no university library can sustainably deliver services to her users in an environment in which her workforce hoards knowledge on the ground of individual self-recognition. It may be argued as posited by Lee and Ahn (2006) that individual-based reward system is more efficient than group-based system noting that in the group-based system, knowledgeable staffs are less likely to share their knowledge. Yes, this may work in a marketing company or organization and not in the university library. The library is a social institutions whose major commodity is information which must be processed and organized in such a way as to satisfying both students, faculty members and other stakeholders information needs thereby making every staff a driver of access to knowledge thus making information sharing in line with the university library culture a necessity. In a different angle, study by university library staff of organizational culture, will no doubt increase their understanding of how it influences other organizational outcomes such as productivity, employee engagement, and commitment. It is in the light of the above that the following recommendations are made:

- Effective management is always the brain-child of a good leader in that good leadership breeds loyal followership. In the course of this study, it was discovered that one or two major factors militating against knowledge sharing in the university library is lack of managerial skills and discriminatory attitude of the university librarians. To this end, university librarians should be made to understand stand their principal role as coordinators, neutral umpires and role model therefore should before assumption of duty have a re-training on the principle of management as most university librarians as observed have no basic knowledge in both human and material resource management. Furthermore, the use of click to run the university library by librarians should be seen as a heinous crime against the profession.
- The act of selfishness as a result of staff idiosyncrasy and lack of trust among staff should be discouraged through orientation and re-training making staff of the library to realize and understand their role as drivers of access to knowledge in which every unit of the library is interwoven therefore everyone must be a team player.
- University libraries should come up with knowledge sharing policy among staff and libraries in that hoarding of knowledge by any library staff in any form and way shall be seen and treated as ‘taboo.’
- In the words of (Tsai, 2011), university librarians must appreciate their role in maintaining or evolving an organization’s culture. A deeply embedded and established culture illustrates how people should behave, which can help employees achieve their goals. This behavioral framework, in turn, ensures higher job satisfaction when an employee feels a leader is helping him or her complete a goal. From this perspective, organizational culture, leadership, and job satisfaction are all inextricably linked. Librarians therefore can create, or influence many different workplace cultures.
- Management of university libraries should note that for them to get the best out of every staff of the library in terms of performance and knowledge sharing, each staff should be seen as more valuable than the organization itself.
- Since organizational culture is not stagnant, university library members of staff should be cultured towards developing a shared belief around “what right looks like” as they interact over time and learn what yields success and what does not. When those beliefs and assumptions lead to less than successful results, the culture must evolve for the

library to stay relevant in a changing environment. The library management members in the course of professing change should have it at the back of their minds that changing organizational culture is not an easy undertaking. Staff members often resist change and can rally against a new culture. Thus, it is the duty of library management to convince their staff of the benefits of change and show through collective experience with new behaviors that the new culture is the best way to operate to yield success and provide sustainable services to the esteemed library users.

- The behavior of the library management needs to symbolize the kinds of values and behaviors that should be realized in every unit/department of the university library on the ground that as change agents, they are keys to the success of this cultural change process and important communicators of new values
- Encouraging staff motivation and loyalty to the library will create a healthy culture. Training and re-training (in the form of further education, seminars, conferences and workshops) should be provided to all staff to help them understand the new processes, expectations, and systems.
- Furthermore, knowledge sharing practices should be envisaged as a major organizational culture that must be seen as prevalent and mandatory for all staff of the university library to follow.
- Going by the identified factors militating against knowledge sharing practices in the library, every policy that inhibits an effective information and knowledge sharing practices should be jettisoned and replaced with practical policy that would enhance the practices.
- Finally, the library management should strengthen staff performance through the institution of reward schemes such as recognition, financial incentives and awards of outstanding performance among others to deserving staff.

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